

Future of E-Commerce in Bangladesh Fashion Industry and Customer Appreciation in E-Commerce

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Accepted November 23,2021
Published November 27,2021

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5733255>

Pages: 183-195

Funding: N/A

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How to cite this article (APA):
Hasan, M. M., & Ronglei, L.
(2021). Future of E-Commerce in Bangladesh Fashion Industry and Customer Appreciation in E-Commerce. *North American Academic Research*, 4(11), 183-195. doi:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5733255>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Background: The future era is running towards the modern innovation that the world is giving every day to ensure a healthy and prosperous life for everyone. Any country nowadays wants to make life easy for the people of their own country well now they can due to E-commerce. Since the birth of fine E-commerce, the usability of the business through the internet it got increased highly within a year and two. With the help of purchasing, managing relationships within buyers and sellers, streaming through online the new products to bring attraction among buyers, developing new communications, and building new business line-up is done so far with the help of this E-commerce.

Materials and Methods: In This article, which focuses on individual audiences, splits the variables that influence the distribution of E-commerce apparel sector marketing into two groups, the 'Internal factor' and the 'External factor'. The non-probability sampling methodology will be used to gather opinions from survey participants. The entire demographic is a social networking consumer group, but the compilation of successful sampling data is limited to the target population, such as young people, graduates, senior people between 18 and 55 years of age, and the sample questions were 37. Overall, it will be easy to justify the fashion E-commerce market for the upcoming generations in Bangladesh by comparing the two groups.

Results: The internal & external factor 2 segment towards e-commerce was comparable and statistically proven significant on its contribution towards fashion e-commerce but 'perceived Human Risk' has its difficulties to set a breakthrough.

Conclusion: To sum up the paper in one sentence consumers' appreciation towards E-commerce is quite positive rather than the old times and further studies can be possible to improve the fashion sectors via more research.

Keywords: E-COMMERCE, RETAILING, MODERN FASHION, ONLINE SHOPPING, ONLINE COMPETITION, CUSTOMER SATISFACTION.

Introduction

E-commerce was derived from an exchange standard between manufacturers and their clients for company records such as orders or invoices. The roots date back to Berlin's 1948-49 blockade and lifts using a commodity

method mostly via telex. In the following decades before the first general standard was issued in 1975, many companies developed this system. The resulting EDI standard is sufficiently scalable to operate the simplest electronic business transactions. The Internet was broadly adopted and in 1991 World Wide Web was launched. In 1993 the first browser was used to use it and the bulk of e-commerce migrated to the Internet.(1)

Figure 1: The Evolution of the E-commerce industry in the last few years.

This origin of e-commerce is older even you assumed it was. Our nation saw a small e-com edition in the late 1990s mostly with the concept of serving NRBs who were searching for a way to give gifts to their precious children in Dhaka. E-commerce began to expand quietly and gradually between 2000 and 2008. The main problems, however, were payment gateways, distribution mechanisms, and consumer education against their exponential growth.(2) The next major security issue was the introduction of Netscape 1.0 in 1994 with a Stable Socket Layer (SSL) protocol that kept sending as well as receiving a secure online transaction. SSL guarantees the protection of sensitive information on the site. Shortly afterward, the first third-party credit card processors began.(3) In the year 2009 Bangladesh Bank enabled the country to pay online thus officially opening up the e-Commerce industry for expansion, rendering e-commerce in Bangladesh a real shift.

Apart from this significant landmark in 2009, the launch of Wi-Max in Bangladesh has led to success in the country and low internet prices.(4) Before 2013, the government prohibited the selling and procurement of foreign credit cards of goods and services online (export.gov, 2017). E-commerce rose 67% in the first three quarters of 2016, while the e-commerce expenditure in the country grew to BDT 359 (Xinhua, 2016). In 2016 the Internet perception rate was 13.2%, with Internet subscribers numbered 66.6 million according to Bangladesh's Telecommunication Regulatory Committee (BTRC). In 2017, there were 80.6 million internet users, while the penetration rate increased to 48.4%. In 2018, there were a further 91.3 million internet users and 52.77% penetration. At present, there have been 96.199 million Internet subscribers (June 2019).

The e-commerce industry of Bangladesh is projected to hit USD 20 billion by 2020, according to market researchers. BRTC statistics of 90.4 million subscribers, 0.06 million WiMAX subscribers, and 5.73 million ISP + PSTN connectors, according to June 2019.(5) As suggested by the information available from the Bangladesh e-commerce Organization, the reach of the e-commerce industry surpassed the Tk 17.0 billion mark in 2017 from Tk 4.0 billions for 2016 (e-CAB). The metric on the market is conditional on hitting Tk 70 billion by 2021. Whatever the case, the volume will be a lot greater than the recent takeover of the leading online

marketplace Daraz by Chinese e-commerce company Alibaba. The e-commerce retail market in Bangladesh expands at 72 percent a month. This group presently comprises 35,000 workers and 25,000 small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs). The amount of industry e-commerce sites and pages of e-commerce is 2,500 and 150,000. The distribution volume is estimated at the retail level at between 15,000 and 20,000 per day.(6)

Literature review

In e-commerce, buyers and sellers are connected via the Internet, which acts as a single platform.(7) According to Ullman (2013), e-commerce refers to the variety of business transactions that may be done online.(8) This category includes any website that is capable of generating revenue (or intends to generate revenue).(9) With the fast growth and adoption of mobile devices, however, this concept may be deemed out of date. According to Minculete (2013), e-commerce and e-business should drop the letter "e" because the usage of e-commerce technology is increasing and they have become a regular element of marketing activities.(10) E-commerce has become the standard method of conducting business (Downing & Liu, 2014), and as social trust grows, it contributes considerably to economic progress (Qu, Pinsonneault, Tomiuk, & Liu, 2015).(11) Furthermore, how international trade is conducted has shifted. Firms that use the Internet have acquired a new level of contact with other businesses and organizations (Tekin, nice, Etlolu, Koyuncuolu, & Tekin, 2018).(12) Ramdhani et al., (2012) said that attitude theories illustrate that consumer attitudes towards a product or service will affect consumer behavior or action against these products or services, marketers need to know the attitude of customers towards the products it markets, and then formulate strategies to influence consumer attitudes.(13) According to Agarwal and Wu (2015), the usage of e-commerce is significant, particularly in firms situated in developed and emerging nations. The examination of previously published research in the subject is essential when assessing the present status of the mentioned issue.(14)

Materials and methods

This future of e-commerce in the Bangladesh fashion industry and customer appreciation study was carried out in Bangladesh from March 2021 to July 2021. A total number of 400 people (both male and female) aged between (18-55), years took participated in this study.

Study Design: This literature review will be followed a survey and grounded theory to assess the efficacy and influence of e-commerce platforms on the fashion goods or services of the target market.

Study Location: The consumer's appreciation on e-commerce study was conducted over different major cities in Bangladesh including – Dhaka, Chattogram, Barishal, Rangpur, Sylhet, Mymensingh, Satkhira, and many more.

Study Duration: March 2021 to July 2021.

Sample size: 400 participants.

Sample size calculation: The data were collected in Bangladesh through an online survey, with support from the students, graduate students, retailers & older people. In total 20 people take the sampling frame during a sampling space of 7 days. In total 400 respondents took part in the survey, resulting in a response rate of 95.24%. Among them, 20 respondents failed to either complete the whole survey.

Subjects & selection method: This article, which focuses on individual audiences, splits the variables that influence the distribution of E-commerce apparel sector marketing into two groups, the 'Internal factor' and the 'External factor'. Among them, the internal factor includes innovation by consumers, personal utility anticipation, and perceived human risk. Moreover, external factor thus includes factors of the commodity for clothing enterprises, website creation, and corporate apparel.

The monogamy model is shown in the figure:

Figure 2: The Monogamy model for this analysis

Descriptive research design:

Qualitative statistics are those which attempt to accurately characterize the behavior of a particular, society. It offers a balancing pad for the study of new regions. This study design is suitable for these experiments because it is versatile enough to give us the below results –

1. It offers resources for analysis of facts of the issue under the report.
2. It determines the terminology of the issue.
3. It offers awareness of the problem area.
4. It helps to overcome the dilemma connected with the conduct of definitive studies.

Sampling:

The non-probability sampling methodology will be used to gather opinions from survey participants. The entire demographic is a social networking consumer group, but the compilation of successful sampling data is limited to the target population. There is very little published research on the growth of fashion clothing’s e-business in Bangladesh. The biggest task was to collect effective knowledge on the issue in numerous national and foreign publications. The interpretation of the results methods is divided into 2 parts:

1. Primary data collection process.
2. Secondary data collection process.

Primary data collection process:

The descriptive analysis methodology was used to collect the relevant evidence and knowledge from the literature available. An analysis by foreign and national firms was carried out in Bangladesh about the future role of e-commerce implementation which was used to gather further information.

I used the questionnaire for primary results.

Secondary data collection process:

The secondary data are collected from the organization's website, from business brochures, from periodicals and documents, from corporate publications, magazines, and newspapers, etc. Secondary information is data previously obtained by someone else that has already been collected by manipulating pre-existing statistical.

Table no 1: Demographic data analysis.

Demographic Data Analysis				
characteristics	Male	Percentage	Female	Percentage
Gender	338	84.50%	62	15.50%
Age	age/percentage in below			
	18-25	26-30	31-40	41-55
	36.80%	38.10%	18.10%	8.30%
Education	Student	Retired	Employed	Unemployed
	116	4	254	26
	29%	1%	63.60%	6.50%
How often do they shop	shopping/percentage			
	Once a week	Once in a month	Once in a year	Randomly
	70	137	40	153
Spending's	spending's/percentage			
	\$0-100	\$100-200	\$200-300	\$300-500
	281	81	19	19
Social media account followings	total follow/percentage			
	(2-4)	(4-6)	(6-8)	More than 8
	212	136	38	14
	53%	34%	9.50%	3.50%

Table no 1 Shows the basic demographic questionnaire answer that was collected from the survey. According to the table the total percentage of 'male' & 'female' are respectively 338 male 84.50% & 62 female 15.50%. Furthermore, if we see the age variation then we can see that the '26-30' range people are the highest with a 38.10% followed by the '18-25' range is holding 36.80%. Moreover, people from '31-40' is only 18.10% and '41-55' ends at 8.30% in total. If we see the educational zone the 'employed' range has the highest form the rest carrying a total 254 people with 63.60% followed by 'student' with 116 & 29% out of 100%. Nevertheless the 'unemployed' & the 'retired' gets down with 26 people 6.50% and 4 people 1% respectively.

Results And Discussion

After 4 months of investigation, this study evaluates how fashion E-commerce has created a noteworthy change during the last couple of years in online marketing. In the comparing of internal & external factors via descriptive deep analysis some crucial data were found to make a clear statement on the current condition of e-

commerce effects for both retailers & consumers.

Innovation By Consumers:

In table 2 three groups were dignified who represent the ‘Innovation by Consumers’ perception towards e-commerce. In the chart ‘Interested in e-commerce’ 91.80% of people are satisfied 8.30% people are dissatisfied. In the next ‘E-commerce fashion following’ 98.20% of people are following different brands page and 1.80% people are not following. In the last 'E-commerce is underrated for its contribution to the economy' 44.10% people are satisfied on the statement 34.30% people are dissatisfied along with 21.80% people gave a neutral answer. So, the final results from here are an innovation by consumers has a positive impact on e-commerce.

Table no2: Innovation by Consumers.

Group	Satisfaction on - Innovation by Consumers %	Dissatisfaction on - Innovation by Consumers %	Neutral %
Interested in e-commerce	91.80%	8.30%	0%
E-commerce fashions following	98.20%	1.80%	0%
E-commerce is underrated for its contribution to the economy	44.10%	34.30%	21.80%

Personal Utility Anticipation:

In table 3 again three groups were dignified who represent the ‘Personal utility anticipation’ perception towards e-commerce. From the below chart the first point 'Prefer most before buying any fashion clothing proves to be satisfying people by 51%, dissatisfying by 49%. Consistently 'Would you be interested in a service that could connect you to the newest e-commerce’ is proving to the agreed side by 76.80% of people and 4% on the negative side along with 19% giving a neutral opinion. As for the last ‘How comfortable will you feel while using e-commerce pages’ proves its satisfying level by 96.30% of people 2.50% saying negative & 1.30% saying neutral respectively. Form here is clear that the ‘Personal utility anticipation’ does satisfy the needs of majority consumers attitude towards e-commerce.

Table no 3: Personal Utility Anticipation.

Group	Satisfaction on - Personal Utility Anticipation %	Dissatisfaction on - Personal Utility Anticipation %	Neutral %
Prefer most before buying	51.00%	49.00%	0%

any fashion clothing's			
Would you be interested in a service that could connect you to the newest e-commerce	76.80%	4.00%	19%
How comfortable will you feel while using e-commerce pages	96.30%	2.50%	1.30%

Perceived Human Risk:

Table 4 represents the 'Perceived human risk' on the contribution to e-commerce. To begin with 'Method of payment you prefer when shopping via e-commerce' is showing the positive answer from the respondent by 50.50% and 49.50% shows negative response on their answer. Following the next question 'Online store to have a physical showroom or store' 77.50% of the respondent shows positive satisfaction only 5.50% presented dissatisfaction as their answer followed by 17% of people who choose to stay on the neutral. But in the last question 'In e-commerce market, marketing practices & socialization has a positive impact' majority people chose to stay with dissatisfied with 89.30%, only 8.30% are thinking as positive with 2.50% on the neutral position. So, 'Perceived human risk' does need some improvements as it is not completely showing its full attitude towards e-commerce.

Table no 4: Perceived Human Risk.

Group	Satisfaction on - Perceived Human Risk %	Dissatisfaction on - Perceived Human Risk %	Neutral %
Method of payment you prefer when shopping via e-commerce	50.50%	49.50%	0%
Online store to have physical showroom or store	77.50%	5.50%	17%
In the e-commerce market, marketing practices & socialization has a positive impact	8.30%	89.30%	2.50%

Factors of The Commodity:

Table no 5 'Factors of The Commodity' is also prepared with three segments of answers which need to be addressed. In the beginning 'E-commerce fashion brands to interact with their customers via social media' significantly showed the satisfaction with 39.80%, same way 22.80% people are dissatisfied & 38% people prove to be kept neutral as their answer. Next is 'Factors attract you to your favorite online e-store' which proves a warping 97.57% of people are very satisfied with the service they are getting now and only a 2.43% proving to be dissatisfied. Not but least 'Social and cultural climate affects e-commerce' has a remarkably positive answer from the respondent with 67% people saying positive, 10.60% people saying negative, at the end of the day 22.50% saying neutral as their persuasion. To sum up the attitudes towards e-commerce are eloquently positive on the factors of the commodity.

Table no 5: Factors of The Commodity.

Group	Satisfaction on - Factors of The Commodity %	Dissatisfaction on - Factors of The Commodity %	Neutral %
E-commerce fashion brands to interact with their customers via social media	39.80%	22.80%	38%
Factors that attract you to your favorite online e-store	97.57%	2.43%	0%
Social and cultural climate affects e-commerce	67.00%	10.60%	22.50%

Web Site Creation:

Table no 6 additionally three more questions need its ceremonious positive an answer to prove its impact on the e-commerce. At the outset ‘Features will be more attractive to you for an online e-store to do so’ meaningfully show that 98.50% of people are complacent and only 1.50% people are exasperated. Moreover ‘E-commerce in Bangladesh still needs improvement’ has an excellent 96% satisfaction only by 4% dissatisfaction rate. Eventually ‘Would you like to see improvements within upcoming years’ 99% of people want to see the improvements within the coming years as every single day's new designs and innovations are taking place just to improve the lifestyle of consumers. Only 1% of people think it's not necessary though. To wrap up website creation has its potential for e-commerce.

Table no 6: Web Site Creation.

Group	Satisfaction on - Web Site Creation %	Dissatisfaction on - Web Site Creation %	Neutral %
Features will be more attractive to you for an online e-store to do so	98.50%	1.50%	0%
E-commerce in Bangladesh still needs improvement	96.00%	4.00%	0%
Would you like to see improvements within upcoming years	99.00%	1.00%	0%

Aspects in Corporate Apparel:

In table 7 three groups were distinguished to illustrate the 'Aspects incorporate Apparel' perception of E-commerce. According to the below chart 'In general, culture is an inspiration for business entrepreneurs' is showing satisfaction by 71.60% only 9.30% on the dissatisfaction & 19.30% as a neutral opinion selector. Furthermore 'To be a good e-commerce entrepreneur, consumer awareness is required' proves to be outstandingly good by 89.30% in addition to 2.50% on the displeasure section along with 8.3% as a neutral respondent. To finish with 'The choice of e-commerce is limited by incompetent conventional market patterns' is selected by 44.50% positive people very close to 43.80% which is a negative and 11.80% as usual on the site with neutral.

Table no 7: Aspects in Corporate Apparel.

Group	Satisfaction on - Aspects in Corporate Apparel	Dissatisfaction on - Aspects in Corporate Apparel	Others
In general, culture is an inspiration for business entrepreneurs	71.60%	9.30%	19.3%
To be a good e-commerce entrepreneur, consumer awareness is required	89.30%	2.50%	8.3%
The choice of e-commerce is limited by incompetent conventional market patterns	44.50%	43.80%	11.80%

Finally, the results show that the internal and external have positively proven to have a great impact on the attitude towards e-commerce. Therefore, the internal factor 'Perceived Human Risk' harms the e-commerce market as still many modifications are needed to be improved by the time ahead so that the consumers can get the ultimate advantages of e-commerce. Except that all the five other factors have a success rate of over 90% positive on the current condition of the e-commerce market in Bangladesh. Eventually, the e-commerce sectors have improved a lot if we compare with the previous years or so, over time it will increase output and provide a competitive advantage. Worldwide, information technology (IT) has encouraged commerce. It is now easier to join a new market and assess the performance of one's product and company. It lowers business overhead and improves business administration.(15)

Conclusion

The most critical aspect required for the growth of e-commerce in Bangladesh is faith. When it comes to the Bangladeshi market, I believe there is a widespread lack of confidence between retailers and buyers. Consumers do not trust retailers because they believe they are being overcharged or that they will not receive enough customer support once the deal is completed. This pervasive loss of faith, in my opinion, is the biggest impediment to the expansion of e-commerce in Bangladesh. More improved practical ways need to improvements for the online shops to increase trust and create an environment where customers feel comfortable pressing the "Proceed to Checkout" button. But still having so many difficulties fashion e-commerce sectors managed to set up their good mark during these current years and with its improvements in the next few years it can establish a footmark with the global leaders like – USA, Canada, UK, China, India, Malaysia and many more.

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